

Co-thinking and Creation for STEAM diversity-gap reduction

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CreaSTEAM Unit Plan Analysis

CreaSTEAM CONSORTIUM

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Introduction

An analysis of the 64 Unit Plans created has been carried out to provide an overview of the type of approach that schools have designed for their STEAM-LABS, not only at the methodological level but also at the level of diversity and instructional design. The analysis done is based on the data collected using the Unit Plan template (Fig.1), created for this project.

The figure shows a 'CreaSTEAM Unit Plan' template on a dark purple background with colorful paper scraps. The form includes the following sections:

- TITLE:** [Blank box]
- DATE:** [Blank box]
- SCHOOL:** [Blank box]
- MAIN TEACHER:** [Blank box]
- AGE LEARNERS:** [Blank box]
- NUMBER OF TEACHING HOURS:** [Blank box]
- CreaSTEAM Unit Plan** (Title in yellow)
- SUBJECTS INVOLVED:** (ENSURE TWO OR MORE)
 - SCIENCE
 - TECHNOLOGY
 - ENGINEERING
 - ARTS
 - MATHS
- IMPLEMENTATION:** (ENSURE ALL)
 - INTERDISCIPLINARY INSTRUCTION
 - EMPHASIS ON CREATIVITY
 - ADDRESSES DIVERSITY GAP (IMMIGRATION / GENDER / ECONOMIC / RELIGION)
- INSTRUCTION:** (ENSURE ONE OR MORE)
 - ACTIVE LEARNING
 - PROJECT BASED LEARNING
 - PERSONALISATION OF LEARNING
 - SERVICE-LEARNING
 - COLLABORATIVE LEARNING
 - DESIGN THINKING METHODOLOGIES
 - INQUIRY BASED LEARNING
 - TINKERING
- SHORT DESCRIPTION:** [Blank box]
- MATERIALS/RESOURCES:** [Blank box]
- LEARNING OBJECTIVES:** [Blank box]
- LESSON PLAN OUTLINE:** [Blank box]
- RESULTS/EVIDENCES:** [Blank box]
- PERSONAL NOTES:** [Blank box]

At the bottom, there are logos for CreaSTEAM, GRETEL, GRIAL, and the European Union, along with the text: 'Co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union'.

Figure 1: Unit Plan template.

Figure 2 shows an overview of all the parameters defined in the Unit Plan template for the 64 practices.

n= 64	Science	Technologies	Engineering	Arts	Math	Other
Total	47	57	32	37	36	34
%	73,44	89,06	50,00	57,81	56,25	53,13

Table 1: STEAM domains worked on.

As can be seen, almost unanimously, almost 90% of the units created have set technology as one of the aspects of their work, followed by approaches linked to the sciences. The arts and mathematics are positioned at around 60% above engineering approaches and other areas of work.

In the Other section, we have included those specific subjects that teachers have decided to identify separately from the main subject areas. The breakdown of these subjects can be found in Table 2.

Social Science	5
Geography	9
Politics	3
Physics	5
Music	4
History	2
Languages	15
Literature	2
Emotional education	3
Sports	3
Civics	5
Citizenship education	1
Geometry	1
Geology	1
Informatics	3

Table 2. Other subjects covered in the 64 Unit Plan.

In this sense, the average obtained is 4.22 subjects/fields of work per Unit Plan designed, which indicates a high degree of multidisciplinary in the practices designed. Analyzing the combinations selected for each Unit Plan, we obtain the following predominance (see Table 3, 4):

Main combinations								
STEAM	STEM	STAM	STEA	TEAM	STE	STM	STA	TAM
8	7	8	4	2	4	3	3	4

Table 3. Main combinations of fields of knowledge.

Other basic combinations	
STE + other	24
STEM + other	15
ST + other	42
TE + other	30
SA + other	27

Table 4. Most commonly used basic combinations.

It is interesting to note the large number of didactic units (around 50%) that have chosen an average of four fields of knowledge, Technology being the predominant one together with science. It is also important to highlight the importance that the combination of technical fields with approaches derived from the Arts has obtained. These results demonstrate that the combination of extreme domains can be a functional strategy for dealing with people with diversity and that they complement each other's knowledge to improve students' motivations and results.

About Curricular Instruction

The next section that parameterized the didactic unit was the type of curricular instruction to be followed. As can be seen in Table 5, interdisciplinary instruction stands out with almost 94% of the applications, followed by those that try to manage aspects of diversity gaps, and finally (but with a percentage of 73%) those that promote the enhancement of student creativity.

	Interdisciplinary Instruct.	Emphasis on creativity	Addresses Diversity Gap
n=64	II	EC	DG
Total	60	47	51
%	93,75	73,44	79,69

Table 5. Unit Plan implementation.

The average of the 64 units created sets a usage of 2.46 out of the 3 items identified, which indicates that it is most useful to create didactic units that directly work with all three approaches. 43 Unit plans (67,19%) have identified the three approaches. The II+DG combination has been defined by 6 units, and in combinations with only one approach, we found 10 with II identified, 2 with, EC, and only one with DG.

If we analyze the results considering the most used STEAM combinations (STEM + STEAM + STAM, n=33), we obtain that the instructions combining the three approaches (II+EC+DG) drop to 69% (23 units), and those with the single approach of II rise to 24%. The two-approximation combinations are only 6%, being II+DG combinations.

Diversity Gap

As we have seen, 80% of the didactic units identified the work on one of the diversity gaps as a fundamental approach. However, 100% of the units designed either worked on an existing diversity in class or carried out a practice focused on raising awareness and/or procedures to improve this diversity. Table 6 shows the distribution of the diversities addressed in the units.

n=64	Diversity GAP				
	Gender	Immigration	Economic	Religion	Disability
Total	46	16	40	7	43
%	71,88	25,00	62,50	10,94	67,19

Table 6. Diversity Gap implementation.

Over 72% of the units worked on gender diversity, which is predominant in other projects and the STEAM scientific literature. With a percentage above 67%, 43 units also pointed out disabilities as aspects to be addressed in STEAM approaches. Both the value of 71.88 for gender and 67.19 for disabilities are relevant, as in one of the first samples taken with 30 didactic units, the percentages of these two gaps were 90% and 56% respectively, indicating the growing

interest in linking STEAM approaches to providing solutions for students affected by disabilities, mental disorders being one of the most common problems.

Finally, the problems derived from the student's social/economic status should also be highlighted, which are addressed by 62.5% of the teaching units. In this sense, STEAM practices seek to improve students' knowledge in a holistic, cross-disciplinary way that does not involve the use of expensive systems and technologies, but rather avoids the traditional barriers of education, such as compulsory books and materials, by creative approaches that allow students to obtain the same competencies with the use of more current disciplinary approaches.

If we analyze the combinations of gaps that are most worked on, we find that 4 units have marked all of them as work/improvement objectives, being the least used combination with 6.25%. At the other extreme, with 23.44% of the units designed, 15 of them have marked gender, economic aspects, and disabilities as the three aspects to work on with the unit designed. Other combinations with significant percentages have been the units that have selected only aspects linked to disabilities (8 units, 12.5% of the total), gender issues (7 units, 10.94%), economic and gender aspects (6 units, 9.38%) and combining gender, immigration, and disability (5 units, 7.81%). The rest of the combinations have been punctually identified, with the average number of gaps selected being 2.38 for the total number of units designed.

As we did with the type of instruction, if we focus on the STEAM combinations most used by the 64 units (STEM + STEAM + STAM, 33 units), the percentages of gaps addressed are like the global analysis: 72.73% deal with gender, followed by disabilities and economic aspects with both at 69.70%. Immigration is already at 27% and religion or other aspects do not exceed 10%. The combination of gender, economic aspects, and disability is again the most identified combination, with 27% of the units working more transversally in STEAM areas, followed on this occasion by those that only focus on disabilities or gender plus economic aspects with 12%.

Teaching Instruction

Finally, regarding the methodological training system used, the teachers had to select those methods to be used in the development of the didactic units (see Table 7).

Teaching Instruction								
n=64	Active Learning	PBL	Personalization of learning and inclusive environment	Service-learning	Collaborative learning	Design thinking methodologies	Inquiry-Based Learning	Tinkering
Total	54	41	29	16	49	32	19	31
%	84,38	64,06	45,31	25,00	76,56	50,00	29,69	48,44

Table 7. Teaching Instruction implementation.

With an average of 4.23 methods per didactic unit, out of a maximum of 8 possible, active learning (with 84.38% of the application, 54 units), followed by collaborative learning (76.56%) and Project Based Learning (with 64%) stand out as the most implemented methods.

15 units, 23.4%, selected 2 methods, being the most used. These two methods have been changing depending on the unit, but the most repeated combinations are active learning together with collaborative learning (7 units), and PBL together with tinkering (4 units).

With 14% (9 units), we find those units that selected 5 work methods per unit, followed by combinations with 3, 4, 6, and even 7 methods that were marked by 12.5% respectively of the designed units (8 units). In this sense, it is worth noting that among the units that selected 7 methods, there is a combination that is repeated 5 times and is one that excludes the service-learning selected by the rest of the methods.

Again, focusing only on the 33 units plan with more common subject STEAM matter approaches, the breakdown of methodologies would be (Table 8):

n=33	Combinations of STEM + STEAM + STAM							
	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DT	IBL	T
Total	25	25	16	11	25	18	12	21
%	75,76	75,76	48,48	33,33	75,76	54,55	36,36	63,64

Table 8. STEAM and Teaching Instruction conjunction.

In this case, practices with active and collaborative learning methods and the use of PBL are equal to about 75% of the identified units. A 21% of these units combine only 2 methods (predominantly PBL and Tinkering, both with 4), but the same percentage is used by those that combine up to 7 methods (predominantly those that use all approaches except service-learning), followed by those that combine 5, with 15%.

Discussion

After analyzing the design and implementation of the 64 didactic units collected, we can propose a series of tips that may be useful for both school staff and even families, especially for students affected by diversity gaps.

The ideal time to design effective, efficient, and satisfactory practices is at a mid-point in the student's school maturation, which we could broadly define as between 8 and 12 years of age. When designing motivating practices, these do not have to be of excessive duration (advisable about 10 hours), divided into sessions, which can be implemented with different methodologies.

Ideally, the aim is to improve concepts linked to any type of science and languages, incorporating the use of technologies and with a design that promotes creativity through designs where the artistic part also weighs the competence assessment. Incorporating applied mathematical concepts into this process is one of the best practices (close to 60%) that we have identified.

The separation of the practices into work sessions makes it possible to apply a different methodology to each of them. For example, initially, the challenge to be solved and the basic resources (PBL) can be set out, so that through experimentation and teamwork (Active and Collaborative learning), the students, defining roles and positions, can add layers of work and information to the statement to be solved. In this sense, it is important to consider the gender, economic-social, and disability focus of the potential students as well as the potential "clients" who will review/use the proposal under development, making the student a participant in the challenges of inclusion in our society.

Under the premise of an activity that complies with what is explained in the previous section, we will be closer to a good STEAM practice that improves diversity gaps, making students, teachers, families, and society aware that multidisciplinary and transversal work provides a flow of knowledge, competences, and skills (especially digital), more adapted to the training and professional requirements of today's society.

Figure 4: STEAM knowledge is attractive, interesting, amazing, needed, and important in education. Pre and post-comparison after teacher training.

Figure 4 shows the result of grouping in a matrix the variables that define how attractive, important, boring, exciting, or fascinating STEAM training is. Positive aspects are added, while negative aspects are subtracted in the development of the STEAM indicator, which ranges from a minimum value (x-axis) of -1 (not important at all) to a maximum value of 19.

The ordinate axis shows the number of overall results. In this sense, the sample analyzed is for a total of 141 teachers who have registered with an anonymous but personal code that has allowed their answers to be matched on the initial and final forms. The sample of teachers who answered the pre-test was 375, and 233 answered the post-test, but only 141 entered the correct information that allowed the matching of their answers. In conclusion, a significant increase in the positive evaluation of STEAM practices in schools can be observed after the training. While initially the maximum values (17-18-19) were very few, after the training they rose significantly, shifting the influence curve of the responses towards the positive end of the options matrix.

Figure 5 shows the variation in the standard deviation of the response matrix analyzed in Figure 4. As can be seen, in addition to increasing the positive assessment (Fig. 4), the deviation between the responses obtained has been decreasing, which indicates that not only is the teachers' perception not significantly improved, but also that there has been a significant increase in the number of responses.

Figure 5: Standard deviation of the response matrix of Figure 4.

Based on the MUSIC Inventory, a system to assess the motivation before and after an action/activity, we have performed other analyses. We have defined the following questions regarding the training (see Fig. 6):

- Q1: I consider that the course will be/has been relevant for my future activities.
- Q2: I consider that I will be able to implement the contents of this training in my teaching.
- Q3: The contents of the training will be/have been useful and interesting.
- Q4: The teacher will be/has been able to guide me and help me in completing the training.
- Q5: Do you think more teachers in your school are interested in implementing robotics in their subjects?

Figure 6: Basic MUSIC Inventory analysis.

As can be seen, there is a significant increase in all variables after training. The results in Figure 6 are complemented by other interesting data collected. For example, to the questions: "Do you think inclusion is an important element in your school's policies?" or "What degree do you think your school addresses the inclusion of every student?" The teachers' perception averages were between 4.6 and 4.2 out of a maximum of 6, but these trends improve after the training with values that are easily above 5 out of 6. For example, the perception that the school management will accept a migration to STEAM systems increases from 4.3 to 4.6, and in the case of this perception on the part of the students, an average of 5.38/6 is reached. The training reaches a rating of 5.38/6 and unanimously expresses an improvement in technological tools applied to STEAM projects and spaces, in new teaching methods and dynamics, and in how all this can improve the attention to diversity gaps.

The final perception of the usefulness of the training for improving classroom diversity gaps can be observed in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Usefulness of the training for improving classroom diversity gaps.

Considering that a Likert scale from 0 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree) was used, it is possible to confirm the high degree of acceptance of the training and the possibilities of adapting it for the creation and use in STEAM spaces and projects, especially focusing on the treatment, improvement and/or training of diversity aspects.

If we only focus on the degree of knowledge that the teacher perceives to have improved as a result of training in STEAM concepts, the result continues to be excellent, as practically all teachers have placed their answers in the high or very high zone of the response scale (see Fig. 8).

Figure 8: Level of perception about the increment of STEAM Tools knowledge after the training.

Conclusions

One of the main objectives was the creation of new STEAM spaces where to develop multidisciplinary practices with attention to diversity, and to reduce any existing gap. To do this, the first step is to train teachers. A trained teacher generates a motivated teacher, capable of implementing new educational processes and attending to diversity with new tools. Teacher training is the first step to obtaining a reference center both in terms of space and attention to diversity. Given the units created through the Unit Plan template, it can be seen how the training in different phases, with different levels and different contents and materials has been adequate, obtaining a reproducible and scalable learning ecosystem in new projects.

The process is not easy and undoubtedly depends on the centers providing options so that their teachers have time for training, and time to design new approaches, new approaches that the more interdisciplinary they are, the more attractive they will be for the students. The type of competencies to be acquired, as well as the methodologies to achieve them, are changing rapidly. Getting teachers trained in new technologies, including those as current as Artificial Intelligence, and using them in a controlled, controlled, and sustainable way in the classroom will result in an increase in the quality of education, the initial and final commitment of the CreaSTEAM consortium.